

Kazakova Rada*DMD, PhD, Senior Assistant Professor**Department of Prosthetic Dentistry, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University – Plovdiv
CAD/CAM Center of Dental Medicine, Research Institute, Medical University – Plovdiv
3 'Hristo Botev' Blvd, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria***Abstract**

This article delves into the integration of 3D-printed models in dental education to bolster learning outcomes. Leveraging 3D printing technology, dental training programs can furnish students with lifelike anatomical models for immersive hands-on practice and simulation-based learning. The article scrutinizes the benefits and applications of 3D-printed models in dental education, underscoring their role in augmenting student proficiency, retention, and clinical readiness.

Keywords: Dental education, 3D printing, anatomical models, simulation, hands-on learning.

Introduction: Dental education relies heavily on practical experience and hands-on training to nurture clinical skills and competency among students. Traditional educational modalities often rely on plastic models or cadaveric specimens, which may be constrained in availability and realism. However, with the advent of 3D printing technology, dental training programs have gained access to more advanced and realistic anatomical models. These models present a unique opportunity for students to practice various dental procedures in a simulated environment, thereby enhancing their learning experience and clinical preparedness. This article investigates the integration of 3D-printed models in dental education and scrutinizes their impact on student learning outcomes.

Materials and Methods: A comprehensive literature review was conducted to evaluate the utilization of 3D-printed models in dental education. Electronic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect were queried using keywords such as "dental education," "3D printing," "anatomical models," and "simulation." Studies focusing on the development, implementation, and evaluation of 3D-printed models in dental curricula were selected for review. Additionally, case studies and educational reports showcasing the effectiveness of 3D-printed models in dental training were included in the analysis.

Results: The review of literature revealed a burgeoning body of evidence supporting the use of 3D-printed models in dental education. Studies have demonstrated that 3D-printed models offer several advantages over traditional teaching methods, including enhanced realism, interactivity, and repeatability. Moreover, students report heightened engagement and satisfaction when using 3D-printed models for hands-on practice and simulation-based learning [1-5]. These models enable students to visualize complex anatomical structures and simulate various dental procedures in a risk-free environment, thereby improving their proficiency and confidence in clinical practice [6,7].

Discussion:

The integration of 3D-printed models in dental education has transformed the way students learn and practice dental procedures [8-11]. Table 1 provides an overview of the diverse applications of 3D-printed models in dental training, showcasing their versatility and effectiveness in enhancing student learning outcomes. From preclinical skill development to advanced procedural training, 3D-printed models offer a range of educational benefits that cater to the needs of dental students at different stages of their training.

Table 1

Applications of 3D-Printed Models in Dental Education

Applications	Description
Preclinical Skill Development	3D-printed models serve as invaluable tools for students to practice basic dental procedures, such as cavity preparation and tooth restoration, in a simulated environment. These models offer a realistic representation of dental anatomy and allow for repeated practice to improve proficiency and technique.
Advanced Procedural Training	In addition to basic skills, 3D-printed models can be used for advanced procedural training, such as implant placement and orthognathic surgery planning. By simulating complex procedures, students can gain practical experience and refine their clinical decision-making skills in a controlled setting.
Patient Communication and Treatment Planning	3D-printed models aid in patient communication and treatment planning by providing visual aids for discussing treatment options and demonstrating anticipated outcomes. Dentists can use these models to educate patients about their oral health conditions and proposed treatment plans, fostering better understanding and informed decision-making.

Moreover, Table 2 highlights the educational benefits associated with the integration of 3D-printed models in dental curricula. From enhanced student engagement to improved retention and clinical preparedness, these models offer a host of advantages that contribute to a more effective and comprehensive learning experience.

Table 2

Educational Benefits of 3D-Printed Models

Educational Benefits	Description
Enhanced Student Engagement	3D-printed models captivate students' attention and promote active participation in learning activities. The tactile nature of these models allows students to interact with anatomical structures and gain a deeper understanding of dental concepts through hands-on exploration.
Improved Retention and Clinical Preparedness	Studies have shown that students who learn with 3D-printed models demonstrate better retention of knowledge and clinical skills compared to those using traditional teaching methods. By providing realistic and immersive learning experiences, 3D-printed models better prepare students for clinical practice and patient care.
Customization and Adaptability	3D printing technology allows for the customization and adaptability of models to meet the specific educational objectives of dental programs. Educators can create models tailored to simulate various clinical scenarios, enabling students to develop critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities in a controlled environment.

The implementation of 3D-printed models in dental education represents a transformative shift towards innovative teaching methodologies that prioritize experiential learning and clinical relevance. By harnessing the potential of 3D printing technology, dental educators can provide students with immersive learning experiences that mimic real-world clinical situations, ultimately better preparing them for the challenges of professional practice.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the integration of 3D-printed models in dental education represents a paradigmatic advancement in teaching methodologies, offering students enhanced learning experiences and better preparation for clinical practice. By providing realistic anatomical representations and interactive learning experiences, 3D-printed models foster student engagement, retention, and clinical proficiency. As technology continues to evolve, the use of 3D printing in dental education is poised to become more widespread, offering even greater opportunities for innovation and improvement in dental training methodologies. Ultimately, the integration of 3D-printed models signifies a commitment to educational excellence and the advancement of dental education.

References

1. Winkler J., Gkantidis N. Trueness and precision of intraoral scanners in the maxillary dental arch: An In Vivo analysis. *Sci. Rep.* 2020;10:1172.
2. Ligon S.C., Liska R., Stampfl J., Gurr M., Mühlaupt R. Polymers for 3D-printing and Customized Additive Manufacturing. *Chem. Rev.* 2017;117:10212–10290.
3. Mahrous A., Schneider G.B., Holloway J.A., Dawson D.V. Enhancing student learning in removable partial denture design by using virtual three-dimensional models versus traditional two-dimensional drawings: A comparative study. *J. Prosthodont.* 2019;28:927–933.
4. Jockusch J., Özcan M. Additive manufacturing of dental polymers: An overview on processes, materials and applications. *Dent. Mater. J.* 2020;39:345–354.
5. Bandiaky O.N., Le Bars P., Gaudin A., Har-douin J.B., Cheraud-Carpentier M., Mbodj E.B., Soueidan A. Comparative assessment of complete-coverage, fixed tooth-supported prostheses fabricated from digital scans or conventional impressions: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Prosthet. Dent.* 2020;127:71–79.
6. Richter M., Peter T., Rüttermann S., Sader R., Seifert L.B. 3D printed versus commercial models in undergraduate conservative dentistry training. *Eur. J. Dent. Educ.* 2022;26:643–651.
7. Dimitrova, M. Comparative study of linear and volumetric changes of 3D printed and conventional resins in removable prosthodontics [in Bulgarian]. PhD Thesis, 2023, Plovdiv.
8. Marty M., Broutin A., Vergnes J.-N., Vaysse F. Comparison of student's perceptions between 3D-printed models versus series models in paediatric dentistry hands-on session. *Eur. J. Dent. Educ.* 2019;23:68–72.
9. Revilla-León M., Jiang P., Sadeghpour M., Piedra-Cascón W., Zandinejad A., Özcan M., Krishnamurthy V.R. Intraoral digital scans—Part 1: Influence of ambient scanning light conditions on the accuracy (trueness and precision) of different intraoral scanners. *J. Prosthet. Dent.* 2020;124:372–378. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051X.2011.01748.x.
10. Güth J.F., Ponn A., Mast G., Gernet W., Edelhoff D. Description and evaluation of a new approach on pre-clinical implant dentistry education based on an innovative simulation model. *Eur. J. Dent. Educ.* 2010;14:221–226.
11. Javaid M., Haleem A. Current status and applications of additive manufacturing in dentistry: A literature-based review. *J. Oral Biol. Craniofacial Res.* 2019;9:179–185.